
Pilot report

DC

QUESTION 1

Taking into consideration the Transformational Modules, what concrete steps did the team take to answer the TMs?

Strategic agenda: Through its investigations of the affordances of artistic research in the fields of art practice, media archaeology, decolonial studies and the VR development and design, the pilot contributed to defining the research carried out by the alliance, i.e. artistic research, and contributes to the research agenda. This will be consolidated in the planned application for a FILM EU Center of Excellence in Immersive Media that will come out of this pilot.

Impact & Engagement: The pilot fostered strong research networks within the alliance and works towards building a joint research agenda. The collaborations with partners - including four different museum in three countries, heritage organisations, five independent artists from African descent and many member from the international academic community – led to joint outcomes with relevant societal impact in the field of problematic heritage, colonial media heritage.

Talent: Several MA and PhD students from within the alliance participated in the research. This experience guides the development of an HR strategy aimed at involving and fostering talented researchers and defining future career paths.

Networking: The development of the pilot and the future ambitions to build a solid joint research structure (center of excellence) will consolidate the efforts made in terms of networking inside and outside the alliance. In addition we can mention that the project led to a structural collaboration with the International Panorama Council and that we have been invited to organize the 2025 IPC conference in Lisbon.

Can you please make one case study specific in which you feel the pilot excelled?

The pilot excelled in several TMs. I would single out impact and engagement. This exemplifies how the strategic research agenda of FILM EU and its focus on the affordances of artistic research leads to outputs with direct societal relevance.

The pilot directly led to the curation of three exhibitions by the research team. These exhibitions demonstrate how artistic practice and artistic research contribute in a direct and unique way to current societal debates, including the debate on colonial heritage and decolonization; questions around propaganda and alternative truths; the uses of contemporary immersive media and AI.

QUESTION 2

Any challenge or barrier to reporting, in particular in these topics, core to the dynamic clusters:

- interinstitutional collaboration:

- In practical terms, the ecological footprint of IRL interinstitutional collaboration is a concern.

- The research teams need to be large enough to be able to foster multiple initiatives stemming from the project (e.g. people working on an exhibition while a partially overlapping group works on the VR development), especially when working with institutions in different countries. In our case, having pilot coordinators from the different institutions was certainly advantageous.

- There was insufficient transparency regarding the HR policies and available FTE in each institution.

- There was insufficient transparency regarding the allocated budget as managed by the different institutions.

- Guidance is needed as to the IP of the artistic deliverables.

- interdisciplinary collaboration:

Interdisciplinarity was at the core of our project. This was a richness rather than a barrier.

- inter-human collaboration :

In general, it takes time to get to know and understand the research cultures in the different institutions within the alliance. We believe this will improve when opted for longer term collaborative structures.

QUESTION 3

What management /collaboration tool did the Pilot Team use? How did the team use it, for what main purpose, and how did you evaluate it?

We were asked to use MS Teams from the beginning of the project. This required multiple logins for the researchers outside of the Lusófona environment and often led to frustration regarding access to folders and individual documents. As such, several WPs (temporarily) moved to other platforms such as Discord and Google Drive. This is not ideal. It is important to adopt one collaboration/management tool for the whole Alliance and to make easy access for individuals from all partner institutions a priority. This may have to be set-up on a dedicated filmeu server.

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1) R&I RESOURCES AND STRATEGIC AGENDA

This module addresses the challenge of defining the profile of the research carried by the Alliance. The specific nature of that research –

artistic practice-based research – implies this module merges the agenda and resources components into one single module. This module entails the development of a concrete roadmap that identifies the actions needed in order to attain the objectives defined both in FILMEU_RIT and under the research agenda already developed in the E+ FILMEU application. This involves developing a common research & innovation agenda and convergence action plan between FILMEU HUB, as the structure that hosts the dynamic clusters, and the objectives and goals of these clusters. This involves pooling expertise, data, and resources and developing a concrete action plan for internationalization, namely in terms of joint actions that can result in new applications and synergies. In order to test the model of the dynamic clusters, the module includes one pilot in each one of the predefined axes of the Hub.

2) IMPACT & ENGAGEMENT

This module addresses the objective of transforming the Alliance into a critical cultural intermediary. This module involves inducing and upscaling cooperation between the innovative networks inside the Alliance and external actors, including associated partners of the Alliance, in order to boost the “Know-Who” dimension in our model. This module involves engaging stakeholders outside of the Alliance in research and innovation in order to produce outcomes that address relevant societal impact. Four pilots are foreseen under the module.

3) TALENT

This module addresses the need to reinforce the competences and research HR critical mass of the Alliance. It involves developing and

implementing strategies for strengthening human capital in research and innovation and for enabling balanced brain circulation via the development of a common human resources strategy. This involves four pilot actions in the form of a common recruitment system that increases the attractiveness of the Alliance; a common system for PhD students' attractiveness and inclusion in R&I activities; and a common system for rewarding researchers.

4) NETWORKING

This module addresses the need for the overall valorisation and legitimization of the Alliance and involves exploring joint structures and sharing best practices across European Universities, facilitating collaboration in activities that could be common to all alliances and generally increasing the ability of the Alliance to intervene at policy-making level. It includes two pilot actions.

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